

AMERICAN ENGLISH AND ITS FEATURES

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Annotation: *The article below gives full information about the origin of the American accent as well as its features*

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In the 17th and 18th centuries, the English language crossed the ocean on ships with British peasants and representatives of the petty and middle bourgeoisie. If we could now return to America at that time, we would have met many immigrants who speak Spanish, French, German, Dutch, Norwegian, Swedish and even Russian.

All these people found themselves in a difficult situation - they had to develop land, build houses, establish production and get used to new natural and socio-economic conditions. They just needed a common language - it was impossible to equip new lands alone, they had to unite, communicate and jointly overcome the obstacles that life put in front of them. The English language became the connecting link between the settlers.

The English language at that time was not homogeneous even within England: strong differences could be noticed in the speech of aristocrats, peasants and the bourgeoisie. Even written English has varied from writer to writer, to say nothing of the representatives of social strata. It was not the refined aristocratic version of English that came to America, but the language of the peasantry and the bourgeoisie.

The settlers faced different problems than the inhabitants of England, they were surrounded by different flora and fauna, history developed in a different way, other things became priority, other qualities were valued in people. The language simply could not help but absorb the realities of life of Americans - and it was changing rapidly.

English today is the most widely spoken, but not the only one, spoken in the United States.

There are far more similarities than differences between American and British English, since they are talking about the same language. However, if you are heading to America, it will be useful for you to know some of the specifics.

In the early days of America, immigrants needed a very simple language to communicate. The already simplified "peasant" English has become even simpler. This is the main difference between American English and British English - simplicity.

The differences in vocabulary are largely the result of the fact that the realities of the Americans were very different from the life of the British. The second most important

factor is the influence of other languages on English in the United States. The strongest influence was exerted by the Spanish, especially in the southwest of the country.

There are words that are widely used in the US but that cannot be heard in the UK and vice versa. When speaking with a modern American, you can hear English words that have long gone out of use in England.

Grammar

The propensity of Americans to simplify things has had a profound effect on grammar. For example, in colloquial speech, you will most likely only hear the tenses of the group Simple (they used to be called "Indefinite" in schools). The chances that your American interlocutor will use Perfect are minimal. This is one of the main reasons why the British consider Americans to be careless about the language. However, this is not entirely fair: Americans are even more inclined to follow many of the grammar rules that the English often neglect.

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